

Reference system for the calibration of MV VTs up to 35 kV and 150 kHz based on parallel-connected generators

Mohamed Agazar, Antonio Delle Femine, *Member, IEEE*, Daniele Gallo, *Member, IEEE*,
Claudio Iodice, *Student Member, IEEE*, Mario Luiso, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—Medium Voltage (MV) grids are experiencing the same Power Quality issues that Low Voltage (LV) grids begun to suffer from some tens of years. In particular, recent advance in semiconductor technology has enabled the development of power converters, directly connectable to MV grids, with higher and higher switching frequencies. Consequently, high-frequency components—specifically, harmonics related to the switching frequency—will be present within MV grids. As happened at LV level, also at MV level it is essential that such disturbances are accurately measured. At the same time, recent international standards set accuracy requirements for Instrument Transformers (ITs) up to 500 kHz. This scenario increased the performance requirements of ITs, particularly in terms of measurement accuracy over an extended frequency range. Unfortunately, no ready-to-use commercial solutions are available to assess the performance of MV ITs up to hundreds of kilohertz. Therefore, this paper presents a reference setup for the calibration of MV Voltage Transformers (VTs), up to 35 kV, at fundamental frequency and in a frequency range from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz. An innovative generation scheme, based on the parallel connection of two voltage sources, allows to generate waveforms composed by a fundamental tone at MV level (up to 35 kV) and by reduced-amplitude spectral components from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz, is proposed. Moreover, also an innovative measuring chain, based on a compensated resistive divider, with the possibility to be cascaded with an additional attenuator or a high-pass filter, is shown. The implementation of the setup is discussed along with the results of the characterization of a commercial MV Low Power VT.

Index Terms—Instrument Transformers, Voltage Transformers, Medium Voltage, Low Power Voltage Transformers, Voltage Divider, High-Frequency, Power System Measurements, High-Frequency Emissions

I. INTRODUCTION

The widespread adoption of switching devices such as inverters, bulky power electronic converters and active filters, used both as loads and as components within generators, particularly in renewable energy systems, has led to

a significant increase of conducted electromagnetic disturbances on grid voltage and current. These disturbances, observable even at the Medium Voltage (MV) level, can extend up to several hundreds of kilohertz as a result of harmonics related to the switching frequencies.

Such high-frequency conducted emissions can interfere with Power Line Communication (PLC), a communication technology extensively employed in power grids to support essential functions, including monitoring, control and automation [1]. This interference degrades the quality and integrity of transmitted information and possible failures of vital grid operations can occur [2]-[4]. High-frequency emissions originating from a single device may couple with other devices, disrupting their control systems and possibly leading to malfunctions or complete operational failures. Additionally, these emissions increase the Root Mean Square (RMS) current, which, along with an intensified skin effect, results in high temperatures and, consequently, accelerates aging and reduces the useful life of components.

Modern power converters, such as Direct Current/Direct Current (DC/DC), Alternating Current/Direct Current (AC/DC), and AC/AC converters, use new generation switching components like Silicon Carbide (SiC) Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistors (MOSFETs) [5], [6]. These technologies enable higher switching frequencies and allow also for direct connection to MV networks. As a result, nowadays MV grids face measurement challenges similar to those already faced in Low Voltage (LV) systems [7]-[10] and that are generally referred to as Power Quality (PQ) measurements. These changes need enhanced performance of measurement systems, especially in terms of accuracy and bandwidth, to ensure reliable operation. Consequently, Instrument Transformers (ITs), namely Voltage and Current Transformers (VTs and CTs), that are the primary elements in nearly all voltage and current measurement chains, must match these evolving requirements.

From a standardization perspective, the existing standards

This work was supported in part by European Partnership on Metrology (EPM) under the projects 22NRM06 ADMIT and 24GRD08 GridForm. The Projects 22NRM06 ADMIT and 24GRD08 GridForm were supported by the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and the Participating States. (*Corresponding author: M. Luiso*).

M. Luiso, A. Delle Femine, D. Gallo, C. Iodice are with the Università degli Studi della Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli", Via Roma 29, 81031 Aversa (CE), Italy (email mario.luiso@unicampania.it, antonio.dellefemine@unicampania.it, daniele.gallo@unicampania.it, claudio.iodice@unicampania.it).

M. Agazar is with the Laboratoire National de métrologie et d'Essais, 1, rue Gaston Boissier, 75724 PARIS Cedex 15, France (email: mohamed.agazar@lne.fr)

governing IT specifications are those belonging to the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) 61869 family; each standard belonging to the family is named a part of the family. Those dealing with accuracy requirements of VTs and CTs for MV and High Voltage (HV) grids are the parts from 1 to 5 and from 9 to 15. Each part is specific for a particular kind of IT, depending on the measured quantity (voltage or current), the technology (inductive or Low Power, LP), the type of output (analogue or digital) and the type of grid (DC or AC). In particular, IEC 61869-1 [11] now extends accuracy requirements to frequencies up to 150 kHz and even 500 kHz. However, these standards do not provide guidance on measurement methodologies, generators architectures, test procedures, reference instrumentation, nor uncertainty evaluation for frequencies beyond the power frequency range [12]. As a result, manufacturers and calibration laboratories retain full discretion in assessing compliance with accuracy specifications above the power frequency, thereby limiting end-users' ability to independently verify product performance.

The activity here presented is developed according to the framework of the European Partnership in Metrology (EPM) 22NRM06 "ADMIT" [13], which aims to establish suitable parameters for the definition of the accuracy of VTs and CTs, and the related measurement instrumentation, in the frequency range up to 150 kHz. In particular, this paper is the extended version of the paper [14], where the architecture of a generation system, able to generate voltage signal composed by a fundamental tone at 50/60 Hz and at MV level, up to 35 kV, with superimposed spectral tones having reduced amplitudes and frequencies between 9 kHz and 150 kHz, is explained and preliminarily tested. Here, other than solving some issues of the architecture presented in [14], the whole measurement setup for the calibration of VTs (whatever the working principle is), with the same amplitude levels and in the same frequency range, is discussed. In particular, the other components of the presented setup are a reference voltage divider, having the possibility to be used with three different output paths, and a comparator. VT calibration is performed by the comparison method.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section II provides a literature review about voltage generation and measurement at MV level and in the frequency range of interest for this paper, that is up to 150 kHz. Section III describes the voltage generation subsystem, obtained by parallel connection of two grounded voltage generators. Section IV presents the voltage measurement subsystem, constituted by a reference voltage divider and a comparator, quantifying also the measurement uncertainty of the whole system. Section V discusses the characterization of two commercial MV VTs, having different working principles, performed with the use of the realized system. Finally, Section VI draws the conclusions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A quite wide literature about the measurement of the frequency behaviour of VTs and CTs beyond the power frequency exists. For brevity, here only some papers are cited [15]-[20]. It is well recognized within the scientific community

that the assessment of the frequency behaviour of ITs requires test signals consisting of a fundamental component (either DC or 50/60 Hz AC), combined with additional spectral components of lower amplitude. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, the frequency range investigated in existing studies is typically limited to 10 kHz. This limitation is likely due to technological constraints, as neither commercial solutions nor custom implementations capable of generating and measuring such composite waveforms beyond a few tens of kilohertz are currently available.

For what concerns the generation of this kind of waveforms, that have a fundamental tone in the MV range and additional spectral components with reduced amplitude and higher frequencies, a generation architecture different from the one proposed in this paper has been proposed in the recent years [20], [21]. It also consists in separating the generation of the power frequency component from the high-frequency components, but using two different generators series-connected. A Step-Up Transformer (SUT) is fed by a low-frequency amplifier to generate the fundamental component at MV level. A high-frequency generator (that is another transformer in [20] and an amplifier in [21]) is connected in series with the secondary winding of the transformer to generate harmonic components. The biggest issues of this architecture are related to the generators grounding and to the high frequency voltage drop across the secondary side of the SUT; the latter is solved by placing a capacitor parallel-connected to the secondary windings of the SUT itself. The setup presented in [20] works up to about 80 kV and 10 kHz, whereas that presented in [21] works up to 3.6 kV and 150 kHz.

For what concerns the reference measuring chain, its first element is a reference VT, mostly a voltage divider, especially when the frequency characterization of the device under test has to be performed. Several implementations of high accurate voltage dividers, up to hundreds or thousands of kilovolt, are presented in literature, f.i. for DC applications [22], [23], for high voltage pulse measurements [24], [25] and for applications similar to that of this paper [20]. In all the cases, they are not compliant with the requirements of the application at hand, due to the limited bandwidth or to the lack of the necessary flatness in the frequency behaviour.

In conclusion, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no solutions already developed for the metrological characterization of MV VTs up to 35 kV and 150 kHz, for what concerns reference devices and generation and measurement setup.

III. VOLTAGE GENERATION

The generation architecture here proposed consists of the parallel connection between the Power Frequency Component (at 50/60 Hz, PFC) generator and the High-Frequency Components (HFCs) generator. The basic block diagram of the proposed solution is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed solution.

It proposes a classical characterization method based on the comparison [15]-[17] of the outputs of a reference VT and of a VT under test, by means of a comparator. Both the comparator as well as the reference VT should have sufficient accuracy in the frequency range from the power frequency up to 150 kHz.

The Power Frequency Generator (PFG) is obtained by means of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG), cascaded by a low-voltage amplifier, cascaded, in turns, by a Step-Up Transformer (SUT) to reach the required voltage levels. Instead, the high-frequency generator is obtained by means of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG), cascaded by another low-voltage amplifier, having an output frequency range from DC up to 150 kHz. The proposed measurement setup is shown in Fig. 2. Looking at Fig. 2, RHVD is the Reference High Voltage Divider, described in Sec. IV.B, Divider 1 (D1) and Divider 2 (D2) are used for the generation subsystem characterization and they are described in Sec. III.B.

As it can be seen from Fig. 2, the sum of the PFC and of the HFCs is simply obtained by the parallel connection of the output of the SUT and of the High-Frequency Amplifier (HFA).

A. Parallel connected Voltage Generators

The applied voltage signals are provided by a two-channels AWG Keysight 33612A (± 10 V). The comparator is realized by a low noise Data Acquisition system (DAQ) PicoScope 4262 (2 channels, ± 20 V, 16 bits, 510 MHz maximum sampling rate, Spurious Free Dynamic Range, SFDR, of 96 dB, memory of 16 megasamples), which acquires the primary and secondary waveforms of the VT under test.

The first AWG channel is connected to a voltage amplifier (± 120 V, ± 50 A, 6 kVA) feeding the VT under test through a 100 V / 35 kV SUT with a rated power of 5 kVA. The second

AWG channel is connected to a power amplifier N4L LPA400 (± 400 V, 50 mA, DC – 1 MHz).

In this generation architecture, it is necessary to protect each generator from the current coming from the other generator. Therefore, two blocking filters have been designed and included.

First, a resistor R1 and a capacitor C1 (rated voltage of 50 kV) are used to protect the SUT from high-frequency current. C1 is a polypropylene film capacitor with voltage coefficient lower than 0.2 % at 50 Hz and linearity error up lower than 0.1 % up to 150 kHz. These components form the blocking element n. 1 (see Fig. 2) and create a low-pass effect with a cutoff frequency equal to $f_{cutoff,1} \cong 636$ Hz, ensuring that HFCs are sufficiently attenuated on the transformer side. Moreover, it should be avoided that an amount of the PFC drops across the resistor R1. Therefore, DUT impedance at 50 Hz (the use of 50 Hz in the equation does not prevent its validity for a 60 Hz fundamental component) should be much larger than R1 resistor. For the values chosen, equations (1) and (2) are derived:

$$|Z_{DUT}(50 \text{ Hz})| = \frac{R1 / (2\pi \cdot 50 \cdot C1)}{\sqrt{R1^2 + \frac{1}{(2\pi \cdot 50)^2 C1^2}}} \quad (1)$$

$$= 30.33 \text{ M}\Omega$$

$$|Z_{DUT}(50 \text{ Hz})| \gg R1 = 100 \text{ k}\Omega \quad (2)$$

Additionally, a HV capacitor, C2 (rated at 50 kV), is placed on the high-frequency amplifier side. It is worthwhile noting that the this capacitor C2 is different with respect to that used in [14]; thanks to this new capacitor, as it is shown in Sec. IV.B, the influence of PFG on HFG operation is strongly reduced with respect to [14]. Along with the output impedance R2 (about 50 Ω) of the amplifier itself, C2 forms the blocking element n. 2 (see Fig. 2) and creates a high-pass effect with a cutoff frequency equal to $f_{cutoff,2} \cong 1.5$ MHz, ensuring that the 50 Hz component is almost totally removed. Moreover, as it was previously stated for blocking element n. 1, it should be avoided that a significant amount of the HFCs drops across the capacitor C2. At high frequency, in fact, there is a voltage partition among C2 and the parallel capacitor made by RHVD and DUT (the capacitance of DUT can derive even by capacitors inside the DUT or by parasitic capacitances that originate inside the DUT itself). For sake of simplicity, considering only the capacitance of RHVD (see

Fig. 2. Generation and measurement setup.

Sec. IV.B), in order to have a reduced drop across C2, the inequality (3) applies.

$$RHVD_{capacitance} = 100 \text{ pF} \ll C2 = 2 \text{ nF} \quad (3)$$

Following the calculation provided in (3), only 5 % of the generated high-frequency voltage drops across capacitors C2, which is acceptable. Obviously, considering also the DUT capacitance, the voltage drop increases.

Blocking elements are not influenced by dividers D1 and D2. Divider D1 has a negligible effect on blocking element n. 1, because C1 is much higher than D1 capacitance. On the other side, divider D2 does not impact the behaviour of the blocking element n. 2, whatever the value of C2.

A picture of the proposed generation and measurement setup is shown in Fig. 3.

B. Characterization of the Generators

In this section the results of experimental tests conducted to quantify the reciprocal influence of the parallel connected generators are shown. To this end, the test procedure involves three steps:

1. both generators are connected, but only the PFG is active;
2. both generators are connected, but only the HFG is active;
3. both generators are connected and active.

PFG is used to generate a PFC at 50 Hz and 12 kV and HFG is used to generate a single HFC with frequency variable from 9 kHz to 150 kHz and amplitude equal to 1 % of the PFC. Therefore, in the following, the first two tests are indicated using the subscript “S” (to address the fact that the resulting waveforms have just a Single tone), whereas the third one is indicated by the subscript “FHF” (to address the fact that the resulting waveforms have a Fundamental tone and a High Frequency tone). In order to execute these tests, three voltages are measured, through RHVD, D1 and D2 connected as shown in Fig. 2 (DUT is not present at this stage). RHVD is described in Sec. IV.B, whereas D1 and D2 are commercial Resistive-Capacitive (RC) dividers, having both ratio of 1000 V/V, accuracy 0.1 % at 50 Hz and 1 % at 150 kHz.

The quantification of the mutual influence of the two generators is done by comparing the amplitudes measured in the first two tests (when a single generator is active and so one single tone is generated at a time) and the amplitude of the component, at the

Fig. 3. Picture of the generation and measurement setup.

same frequency, of the resulting waveform measured in the third test (when two generators are active and two tones are generated simultaneously), specifically by evaluating the voltage deviation defined in (4),

$$\Delta V(f) = \frac{V_{FHF}(f) - V_S(f)}{V_S(f)} \quad (4)$$

where:

- $V_{FHF}(f)$ is the measured voltage at frequency f under the FHF test;
- $V_S(f)$ is the measured voltage at frequency f under the S tests.

In Fig. 3, the influence of PFG on HFG can be seen: it provides the behaviour of $\Delta V(f)$, evaluated at the frequency of the HFC, as function of the same HFC frequency. It is always negative; this means that C2, due to its voltage dependence, when PFG is active, has a lower value (and so a higher impedance), causing a higher HFC voltage drop across C2. Moreover, its maximum absolute value is lower than 0.5 %, that means that the influence of PFG on HFG is quite small. This result represents also an improvement with respect to [14], where a maximum voltage deviation of about 6 % was measured.

Fig. 4. Influence of the PFG on HFG: HFC voltage deviation as function of frequency.

Fig. 5. Influence of the HFG on PFG: PFC voltage deviation as function of frequency.

In Fig. 4, the influence of HFG on PFG can be seen: it provides the behaviour of $\Delta V(f)$, evaluated at 50 Hz, as function of the HFC frequency. It can be observed that is contained in the range $\pm 0.1\%$, implying a not significant influence of the HFG on the PFG. Overall, it can be concluded that thanks to the blocking elements, the mutual influence of the two generators, is very limited, always lower than 0.5 %.

IV. VOLTAGE MEASUREMENT

A. Issues in the design of voltage dividers for high-frequency applications

The design of a high-voltage divider capable of accurately measuring the 50 Hz fundamental component while simultaneously capturing low-amplitude components up to 150 kHz involves a series of interrelated technical challenges. These challenges arise from the conflicting requirements associated with high-voltage operation, wideband frequency response, electromagnetic immunity and stringent uncertainty expectations. Achieving reliable measurements under these conditions requires a careful balance between electrical design, mechanical configuration and digital acquisition performance.

A first difficulty concerns the choice of the high-voltage capacitive arm. Its capacitance must be sufficiently large to limit proximity effects caused by parasitic capacitances between the divider head and ground which otherwise lead to variations in the ratio and phase. However, increasing this capacitance is not without consequence: when high-frequency signals or harmonic content are applied, a large capacitive load can saturate the HF generator, distort the injected signal and reduce the effective bandwidth of generator. The design must therefore find a compromise between stability at low frequency and compatibility with the HF generator, ensuring that the divider remains accurate at 50 Hz while still allowing harmonic measurements up to 150 kHz.

Another critical aspect is the sensitivity to electromagnetic disturbances. Especially when HFCs have very low amplitude (lower than 0.1 %), any external noise that couples with the divider, or noise generated internally by its components, can strongly alter the amplitudes of the HFCs. In these cases, a possible solution is represented by the use of a voltage divider with a low ratio and with a high-pass behaviour, like the one proposed in [21]: in this way, filtering the PFC, it is possible to have, at the output of the divider, HFCs with quite high amplitudes, with respect to the case of a divider with a high ratio and nearly flat frequency behaviour. Generally speaking, the divider must therefore be designed with careful control of its geometry, shielding, grounding and internal connections to avoid that it could behave as an antenna. The minimization of capacitive and inductive couplings and, at the same time the maximization of the electromagnetic immunity are essential to maintain accuracy and repeatability.

As regards the uncertainty, the overall uncertainty is the result of a compromise between the influence of stray capacitances (on the high voltage arm and low voltage arm), high-frequency response with extreme low noise, electromagnetic immunity and digitizer (used as comparator)

performance. Therefore, the design of a high-voltage divider that simultaneously ensures high accuracy at 50 Hz and reliable HFCs measurement up to 150 kHz represents a significant metrological challenge. It requires a comprehensive optimization strategy that integrates electrical modeling, mechanical configuration, filtering techniques, shielding practices and advanced digital acquisition. Such a system must balance inherently conflicting constraints while maintaining a level of uncertainty compatible with high-accuracy applications.

B. Description of the measuring system

The reference voltage measuring system used in this paper was designed and realized by some of the authors of this paper and the design and the realization is extensively described in [26]. Here, for sake of clarity and completeness, its description is briefly recalled, whereas Sec. IV.C shows its experimental characterization and Sec. IV.D the uncertainty evaluation.

The developed measuring system consists of a RC Reference HV Divider (RHVD), having total resistance of 100 M Ω , total capacitance of 100 pF, maximum input voltage of 50 kV_{pk}, rated ratio of 500 V/V and rated bandwidth DC-1 MHz. The ratio has a relatively small value in order to maintain a good signal-to-noise ratio. The output of the divider can then be routed, in turns, through two different paths. The first path uses an attenuator, that is a RC divider (1 M Ω /30 pF), having rated input voltage of 200 V, ratio of 100 V/V and bandwidth DC-1 MHz. It is intended to adapt the output of the RHVD to the input range of most data acquisition systems, that typically is in the order of some volt or even less. In fact, in this way, at the maximum input voltage, that is 50 kV_{pk}, the output of the RHVD cascaded with the attenuator is 1 V_{pk}. This path, as the output of the divider alone, is intended for the simultaneous measurement of all the spectral components of the input waveform, so including the fundamental tone at DC or AC (50/60 Hz) and the higher frequency components. However, when high frequency spectral components having low amplitude (lower than 0.1 % of the fundamental tone) are superimposed to the fundamental tone, the measurement accuracy of such components will decrease. Therefore, in these cases, a second path, constituted by a fourth-order passive high-pass RC filter, having rated input voltage of 200 V, cutoff frequency of about 2 kHz, and attenuation of about 85 dB at 50 Hz, is used. Its scope is to strongly attenuate the fundamental component and so to allow to accurately measure high frequency components with low amplitude.

C. Characterization of the reference divider and of the two output paths

In this section, experimental results related to the characterization of setup's measuring devices (RHVD, attenuator and filter) are provided.

About the RHVD, three tests have been carried out:

- 1) DC amplitude sweep (1 – 50 kV).
- 2) AC amplitude sweep (50 Hz, 1 – 35 kV).
- 3) AC frequency sweep (50 Hz – 150 kHz, 200 V).

It is worth noting that similar procedures for the full

frequency characterization of reference dividers are followed by various National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) around the world, as shown in [20], [21], [24], [27].

Table I summarizes the main features of each test carried out on the high-voltage divider.

The results of test #1, #2 and #3 are provided in Table II, Table III and Table IV, respectively. In test #1, RHVD DC scale factor is measured from 1 kV to 50 kV. In test #2, RHVD capacitance is measured at 50 Hz from 1 kV to 35 kV. As RHVD characteristic frequency (that indicates approximately the frequency value after which the behaviour begins to become dominated by the capacitances) is equal to $f = 1/2\pi RC \cong 16$ Hz, its capacitance is assumed to be a good indication of scale factor variations at 50 Hz. In test #3, scale factor and phase error are measured from 50 Hz to 150 kHz at 200 V.

In test #1, scale factor deviation from 1 kV to 50 kV at DC, for an application time of 1 minute, is 0.01%. Scale factor deviation at 50 kV DC before and after an application time of 10 minutes is 0.0004%, showing that the divider is not significantly influenced by self-heating phenomena. In test #2, capacitance deviation at 50 Hz from 1 kV to 35 kV is 0.03%. In test #3, scale factor and phase error deviations from 50 Hz to 150 kHz are 0.2% and 55 mrad, respectively. In summary, the high-voltage divider shows very good performance for both AC

TABLE I. OVERVIEW OF TESTS ON THE HIGH-VOLTAGE DIVIDER

Test	Frequency	Voltage	Measured quantities
#1	DC	1 – 50 kV	Scale factor
#2	50 Hz	1 – 35 kV	Capacitance
#3	50 Hz – 150 kHz	200 V	Scale factor, phase error

TABLE II. TEST #1: RESULTS

Amplitude (kV)	Application time (min)	Scale factor (V/V)
1	1	500.86
10	1	500.88
20	1	500.86
30	1	500.85
40	1	500.84
50	1	500.83
50	10	500.82

TABLE III. TEST #2: RESULTS

Amplitude (kV)	Frequency (Hz)	C (pF)
1	50	99.27
5	50	99.27
10	50	99.26
15	50	99.25
20	50	99.25
25	50	99.24
30	50	99.24
35	50	99.24

TABLE IV. TEST #3: RESULTS

Frequency (kHz)	Amplitude (V)	Scale factor (V/V)	Phase error (mrad)
0.05	200	500.73	2.11
1	200	500.35	1.52
10	200	500.34	-4.10
20	200	500.30	-7.74
50	200	500.20	-18.07
70	200	500.19	-25.12
100	200	499.98	-35.81
150	200	499.82	-53.35

and DC voltage dependence and flatness in the frequency range of interest.

About the attenuator, just one test has been carried out, that is an AC frequency sweep test from DC to 150 kHz at 200 V. For the attenuator, amplitude sweep tests are not necessary, because it is designed to be used at low-voltage only.

In test #4, attenuator's scale factor and phase error are measured from DC to 150 kHz at 200 V. Test #4 results are provided in Table V. In test #4, scale factor deviation from DC to 150 kHz is 0.02 % and phase error deviation from 50 Hz to 150 kHz is 21 mrad. This shows that the attenuator's frequency response is almost flat in the frequency range of interest.

About the filter, just one test has been carried out, that is an AC frequency sweep test from 1 kHz to 150 kHz at 200 V. For the filter, amplitude sweep tests are not necessary, because it is designed to be used at low-voltage only. Moreover, as it is a high-pass filter, DC and 50 Hz tests are not needed as well. Test #5 results are provided in Table VI.

In test #5, please note that, even though filter's frequency response should be flat in its passband, actually it is not, because a voltage partition effect occurs between filter's capacitor and the overall capacitance of what is connected at filter's output (DAQ input capacitance, cables, connectors, etc.). However, if the setup is used in the same configuration, the errors in Table VI are systematic and so they can be compensated to improve the overall uncertainty.

D. Uncertainty estimation of measuring devices

Three uncertainty sources have been identified for scale factors and phase errors of high-voltage divider, attenuator and filter:

- 1) The contribution of DAQ channels (from LNE calibration).
- 2) The contribution of voltage dependence (which, of course, is null for attenuator and filter for the reasons explained in Section IV.C).
- 3) The contribution associated with repeatability and stability, which becomes more relevant at high frequency,

TABLE V. TEST #4: RESULTS

Frequency (kHz)	Amplitude (V)	Scale factor (V/V)	Phase error (mrad)
DC	200	102.62	-
0.05	200	102.62	0.21
1	200	102.61	0.85
10	200	102.53	6.90
20	200	102.52	1.74
50	200	102.55	-5.88
70	200	102.56	-9.44
100	200	102.58	-14.32
150	200	102.60	-21.63

TABLE VI. TEST #5: RESULTS

Frequency (kHz)	Amplitude (V)	Scale factor (V/V)	Phase error (rad)
1	200	2.31	1.38
10	200	1.92	0.97
20	200	1.49	0.56
50	200	1.35	0.24
70	200	1.34	0.17
100	200	1.33	0.12
150	200	1.33	0.08

whereby the effect of unintended stray parameters is more impactful.

Table VII and Table VIII provide the uncertainty estimation, respectively, for scale factors and phase errors of the high-voltage divider, attenuator and filter.

V. TEST OF A COMMERCIAL VT

As an application of the realized generation and measurement setup, the frequency characterization of a commercial LPVT has been performed. VT's main features are summarized in Table IX. For the VT under test, frequency calibration has been carried out by using all the three measurement chains described in Sec. IV.B:

- 1) Chain n. 1: high-voltage divider only.
- 2) Chain n. 2: high-voltage divider + attenuator.
- 3) Chain n. 3: high-voltage divider + filter.

The generated test waveforms are of FH1 type (Fundamental plus 1 Harmonic, [16]): they are made up of the fundamental tone at 50 Hz and 7 kV and one harmonic tone with amplitude of 1 % of fundamental tone and frequency in the range [9, 150] kHz. Ratio and phase error of VTs under test are measured as in (9) and in (10), respectively:

$$\varepsilon(f) = \frac{k_r \cdot V_s(f)}{V_p(f)} - 1 \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta\varphi(f) = \varphi_s(f) - \varphi_p(f) \quad (10)$$

The results are compared to determine to what extent the three measurement chains are compatible with each other.

A. Uncertainty estimation associated with VT's calibration

Before comparing the results of VTs' calibration, it is necessary to discuss the associated measurement model and uncertainty.

The three complex gains of a DUT measured by the three

TABLE VII. SCALE FACTOR UNCERTAINTY ESTIMATION OF THE HIGH-VOLTAGE DIVIDER, ATTENUATOR AND FILTER

Frequency (kHz)	$u_{SF,RHVD}$ ($\mu V/V$)	$u_{SF,A}$ ($\mu V/V$)	$u_{SF,F}$ ($\mu V/V$)
0.05	50	30	-
10	200	300	450
20	350	300	800
50	800	400	1500
70	1000	400	2200
100	1300	600	3000
150	1500	1200	4500

TABLE VIII. PHASE ERROR UNCERTAINTY ESTIMATION OF THE HIGH-VOLTAGE DIVIDER, ATTENUATOR AND FILTER

Frequency (kHz)	$u_{\phi,RHVD}$ (μrad)	$u_{\phi,A}$ (μrad)	$u_{\phi,F}$ (μrad)
0.05	50	30	-
10	250	150	500
20	400	150	750
50	650	250	1300
70	1000	400	2500
100	1500	600	3000
150	1800	850	4600

TABLE IX. SPECIFICATIONS OF THE TESTED LPVT

VT #1	Rated primary voltage (kV)	Rated secondary voltage (V)	Accuracy class	Technology
	20/ $\sqrt{3}$	3.25/ $\sqrt{3}$	0.5	Resistive

measurement chains ($\hat{G}_{DUT,1}$, $\hat{G}_{DUT,2}$, $\hat{G}_{DUT,3}$) can be expressed as in (7)-(9):

$$\hat{G}_{DUT,1} = \frac{\bar{V}_{chY}}{\bar{V}_{chX}} \hat{G}_{HVD} \hat{K}_{acq,YX} \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{G}_{DUT,2} = \frac{\bar{V}_{chY}}{\bar{V}_{chX}} \hat{G}_{HVD} \hat{G}_A \hat{K}_{acq,YX} \quad (8)$$

$$\hat{G}_{DUT,3} = \frac{\bar{V}_{chY}}{\bar{V}_{chX}} \hat{G}_{HVD} \hat{G}_F \hat{K}_{acq,YX} \quad (9)$$

where:

- \bar{V}_{chX} and \bar{V}_{chY} are the voltage phasors acquired by, respectively, the channels X and Y of the DAQ.
- \hat{G}_{RHVD} is the RHVD complex gain.
- \hat{G}_A is the attenuator's complex gain.
- \hat{G}_F is the filter's complex gain.
- $\hat{K}_{acq,YX}$ is the complex ratio between DAQ channels Y and X .

Table X and Table XI provide, respectively, the uncertainty estimation on ratio and phase errors, for each source at several frequencies.

A repeatability and stability contribution (referred to as R & S), which deals with the influence of stray parameters on results' repeatability, is included too. The last rows of Table X and Table XI provide the combined standard (u_c) and expanded uncertainty (U_c , level of confidence 95%) associated with ratio and phase error of VTs under test. Combined standard ($u_{c,i}$) and expanded ($U_{c,i}$) uncertainty are referred to i -th measurement chain, as previously defined. Moreover, uncertainties associated with the three measurement chains are highlighted in red, blue and yellow, respectively.

B. Frequency calibration of a commercial VT

First, ratio and phase errors at 50 Hz are measured and shown in Table XII. For both ratio and phase error, the results from the two measurement chains involved are well overlapped within their expanded uncertainty. This shows that the addition of an attenuator (i.e., a low-voltage divider) does not degrade the accuracy of the measurement chain at 50 Hz.

Then, VT's ratio and phase errors at high-frequency are measured and shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7.

For both ratio and phase errors, the results of the first two measurement chains (RHVD only and RHVD + A) are well overlapped within their expanded uncertainty. For what concerns the third measurement chain (RHVD+F) the overlap with the other two chains, for both ratio and phase errors, is worse, but the compatibility of the measurements is preserved over the entire frequency range. This issue could be related to the fact that the output capacitance of the filter is quite low, i.e. 220 pF, and so it can be influenced by stray capacitances (due, f.i., to cables, circuit assembly, and so on) which contribute to increase uncertainty as well. As it is explained in [26], this value was chosen as a trade-off. In fact, fixing the cut-off frequency of the filter, the product between the resistance and the capacitance remains fixed, in turns. If the value of the capacitance is kept high, to reduce the influence of the stray

TABLE X. RATIO ERROR UNCERTAINTY ESTIMATION

Sources	Frequency (kHz)						
	0.05	10	50	70	100	150	
u_{HVD} ($\mu V/V$)	50	200	800	1000	1300	1500	
u_A ($\mu V/V$)	30	300	400	400	600	1200	
u_F ($\mu V/V$)	-	450	1500	2200	3000	4500	
$u_{K_{acq}}$ ($\mu V/V$)	40	40	120	250	400	400	
R. & S. ($\mu V/V$)	10	30	50	80	100	200	
Chain 1	$u_{c,1}$ ($\mu V/V$)	60	200	800	1000	1350	1600
	$U_{c,1}$ (95%) ($\mu V/V$)	120	400	1600	2000	2700	3200
Chain 2	$u_{c,2}$ ($\mu V/V$)	70	350	900	1100	1500	2000
	$U_{c,2}$ (95%) ($\mu V/V$)	140	700	1800	2200	3000	4000
Chain 3	$u_{c,3}$ ($\mu V/V$)	-	500	1700	2500	3200	5000
	$U_{c,3}$ (95%) ($\mu V/V$)	-	1000	3400	5000	6400	10000

TABLE XI. PHASE ERROR UNCERTAINTY ESTIMATION

Sources	Frequency (kHz)						
	0.05	10	50	70	100	150	
u_{HVD} (μrad)	50	250	650	1000	1500	1800	
u_A (μrad)	30	150	250	400	600	850	
u_F (μrad)	-	500	1300	2500	3000	4600	
$u_{K_{acq}}$ (μrad)	40	40	120	250	400	400	
R. & S. (μrad)	10	50	150	200	300	300	
Chain 1	$u_{c,1}$ (μrad)	60	250	700	1000	1600	1900
	$U_{c,1}$ (95%) (μrad)	120	500	1400	2000	3200	3800
Chain 2	$u_{c,2}$ (μrad)	60	250	700	1000	1600	1900
	$U_{c,2}$ (95%) (μrad)	140	600	1400	2200	3400	4000
Chain 3	$u_{c,3}$ (μrad)	-	600	1500	2700	3500	5000
	$U_{c,3}$ (95%) (μrad)	-	1200	3000	5400	7000	10000

capacitances, then a low value for the resistance is needed. However, on the other side, a low value for the resistance represents an increased load for the divider, thus influencing its frequency behavior. This is why trade-off values for resistance and capacitance were chosen.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented a reference generation and measurement setup for the frequency characterizations of MV VTs up to 35 kV, at 50/60 Hz and from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz.

The major outcomes of this paper can be summarized as follows.

The proposed generation system is based on the separate generation of the 50 Hz fundamental tone and the high frequency components. The two generators are grounded and parallel-connected to obtain the composed voltage

waveform. Two blocking elements have been added to the setup to prevent current flows from one generator to the other. The mutual influence of the two generators is lower than 0.5 %.

The measurement of the generated voltage is done through a specifically designed RC divider with three possible output paths, two that allow to measure the entire spectrum of the waveform and one that strongly attenuates the fundamental component, allowing for the accurate measurement of spectral components with low amplitude (lower than 0.1 % of the fundamental tone).

An extensive experimental activity for the system characterization has led to the quantification of the measurement uncertainty ranging from 0.32 % up to 1.0 % and from 3.8 mrad up to 10 mrad, respectively for ratio and phase

TABLE XII. RATIO AND PHASE ERROR AT 50 HZ OF THE VT UNDER TEST

	Ratio error	Phase error
Chain n. 1 (RHVD only)	$(0.147 \pm 0.012) \%$	$(4.93 \pm 0.12) \text{ mrad}$
Chain n. 2 (RHVD + attenuator)	$(0.146 \pm 0.014) \%$	$(4.94 \pm 0.14) \text{ mrad}$

Fig. 6. Ratio error of VT under test.

Fig. 7. Phase error of VT under test.

errors, up to 150 kHz, depending on the used measurement path (RHVD alone, RHVD+attenuator, RHVD+filter).

As an application, a commercial MV LPVT was characterized using the different configurations of the system. All the obtained results are compatible within the measurement uncertainty.

In conclusion, the proposed system can be used for the calibration of MV VTs up to 35 kV, at 50/60 Hz and from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz with a measurement uncertainty lower than 0.02 % and 140 μ rad at 50 Hz and lower than 1.0 % and 10 mrad up to 150 kHz, so compliant with the requirements of IEC 61869 family standards [11] for the wideband calibration (WB3) of class 0.1 MV VTs.

REFERENCES

- [1] "IEC 62488 Standard family, "Power line communication systems for power utility applications".
- [2] P. Kotsampopoulos et al., "EMC Issues in the Interaction Between Smart Meters and Power-Electronic Interfaces," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 822-831, April 2017
- [3] S. K. Rönnerberg, A. G. -d. Castro, M. H. J. Bollen, A. Moreno-Munoz and E. Romero-Cadaval, "Supraharmonics from power electronics converters," 2015 9th International Conference on Compatibility and Power Electronics (CPE), Costa da Caparica, Portugal, 2015, pp. 539-544.
- [4] Sarah K. Rönnerberg, Math H.J. Bollen, Hortensia Amaris, Gary W. Chang, Irene Y.H. Gu, Łukasz H. Kocewiak, Jan Meyer, Magnus Olofsson, Paulo F. Ribeiro, Jan Desmet, "On waveform distortion in the frequency range of 2kHz–150kHz—Review and research challenges", *Electric Power Systems Research*, Volume 150, 2017, Pages 1-10
- [5] Y. Xia, J. Roy and R. Ayyanar, "Optimal Variable Switching Frequency Scheme to Reduce Loss of Single-Phase Grid-Connected Inverter With Unipolar and Bipolar PWM," in *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1013-1026, Feb. 2021.
- [6] "Z. Lu et al., "Medium Voltage Soft-Switching DC/DC Converter With Series-Connected SiC MOSFETs," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 1451-1462, Feb. 2021".
- [7] E. O. A. Larsson, M. H. J. Bollen, M. G. Wahlberg, C. M. Lundmark and S. K. Rönnerberg, "Measurements of High-Frequency (2–150 kHz) Distortion in Low-Voltage Networks," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 1749-1757, July 2010
- [8] V. Khokhlov, J. Meyer, A. Grevener, T. Busatto and S. Rönnerberg, "Comparison of Measurement Methods for the Frequency Range 2–150 kHz (Supraharmonics) Based on the Present Standards Framework," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 77618-77630, 2020
- [9] S. T. Y. Alfalahi et al., "Supraharmonics in Power Grid: Identification, Standards, and Measurement Techniques," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 103677-103690, 2021
- [10] A. J. Collin, A. Delle Femine, C. Landi, R. Langella, M. Luiso and A. Testa, "The Role of Supply Conditions on the Measurement of High-Frequency Emissions," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 69, no. 9, pp. 6667-6676, Sept. 2020
- [11] IEC 61869-1:2023, "Instrument transformers - Part 1: General requirements".
- [12] M. Agazar et al., "Power Grids and Instrument Transformers up to 150 kHz: A Review of Literature and Standards", *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 13, p. 4148, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.3390/s24134148.
- [13] EPM 22NRM06 ADMIT, https://www.euramet.org/news-events-seg/details-news?tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Bnews%5D=1743&ccHash=3dec4ab74ccb4d5c668e69d243abf8fc [online on 5 June 2023]
- [14] M. Agazar, A. Delle Femine, D. Gallo, C. Iodice and M. Luiso, "Parallel-Connected Voltage Generators for the Characterization of MV VTs up to 150 kHz," 2025 IEEE 15th International Workshop on Applied Measurements for Power Systems (AMPS), Bucharest, Romania, 2025, pp. 1-6
- [15] G. D'Avanzo et al., "Theory and Experimental Validation of Two Techniques for Compensating VT Nonlinearities," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 71, pp. 1-12, 2022, Art no. 9001312
- [16] G. Crotti, G. D'Avanzo, P. S. Letizia and M. Luiso, "The Use of Voltage Transformers for the Measurement of Power System Subharmonics in Compliance With International Standards," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 71, pp. 1-12, 2022, Art no. 9005912.
- [17] M. Faifer, A. Ferrero, C. Laurano, R. Ottoboni, S. Toscani and M. Zanoni, "An Innovative Approach to Express Uncertainty Introduced by Voltage Transformers," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 69, no. 9, pp. 6696-6703, Sept. 2020.
- [18] A. Mingotti, L. Peretto and R. Tinarelli, "Effects of Multiple Influence Quantities on Rogowski-Coil-Type Current Transformers," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 69, no. 7, pp. 4827-4834, July 2020.
- [19] R. Stiegler and J. Meyer, "Impact of external influences on the frequency dependent transfer ratio of resin cast MV voltage instrument transformers," 2022 20th International Conference on Harmonics & Quality of Power (ICHQP), Naples, Italy, 2022, pp. 1-6
- [20] I. Jayathilaka et al., "Calibration System for High-Voltage Transformers With Multiharmonic Distorted Waveforms," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 73, pp. 1-13, 2024, Art no. 1501013, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2024.3370744.
- [21] G. Crotti et al., "A Novel Generation and Measurement Setup for the Characterization of MV Voltage Transformers from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 73, pp. 1-11, 2024, Art no. 9004711, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2024.3427768.
- [22] A. Merev and J. K. Hällström, "A Reference System for Measuring High-DC Voltage Based on Voltage References," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 184-189, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2014.2338673.
- [23] R. Marx, "New concept of PTBs standard divider for direct voltages of up to 100 kV," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 426-429, April 2001, doi: 10.1109/19.918158.
- [24] J. Hällström et al., "Performance of a Modular Wideband HVDC Reference Divider for Voltages up to 1000 kV," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 64, no. 6, pp. 1390-1397, June 2015.
- [25] J. Hällström et al., "Performance of a Wideband 200-kV HVDC Reference Divider Module," in *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 63, no. 9, pp. 2264-2270, Sept. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2014.2304857.
- [26] M. Agazar, C. Iodice, M. Luiso, "Reference High-Voltage Sensing Chain for the Assessment of Class 0.1-WB3 Instrument Transformers in the Frequency Range up to 150 kHz According to IEC 61869", *Sensors* 2025, 25, 6416. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s25206416>
- [27] G. Crotti et al., "Frequency Compliance of MV Voltage Sensors for Smart Grid Application," in *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 17, no. 23, pp. 7621-7629, 1 Dec. 2017